

PUNTO CRÍTICO

JANUARY - MARCH 2024
ISSUE 9

Me
CCS
PLATAFORMA MEXICANA
DE CAPTURA Y
ALMACENAMIENTO
DE CO₂

PUNTO CRÍTICO

Editorial Committee

Editor
Jazmín Mota

Editorial design
Héctor Ortega

Writing/collaboration
Angélica Quevedo
Lorena Morales
Dulce Martínez
Rodolfo Silva
Laura Escobar
Valeria Chávez
Ismael Mariño

Cover:
NASA, Unsplash

MeCCS
The Mexican Carbon Capture
Platform

<https://meccs.org.mx/>

✉ puntocritico@meccs.org.mx
🌐 [linkedin.com/company/meccs](https://www.linkedin.com/company/meccs)
📷 @MeCCS.plataforma

CDMX, México.
© PUNTO CRÍTICO, 2023
DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10547302

Editor's note

Karen Blixen said that "the cure for anything is salt water: sweat, tears or the sea", but what happens if we don't have water? Water's tangible and intangible value makes it a key element for transforming the environment and countless elements of nature, including people. Unsurprisingly, many cultures attribute powers over emotions and the spirit to it when life itself arises from it. In this issue, we decided to address some of the many aspects of water, starting with a note from Angélica Quevedo of the Gonzalo Río Arronte Foundation that addresses the challenges of water management projects. Afterwards, we have a note by Valeria Chávez, Ismael Mariño and Rodolfo Silva about energy generation from ocean currents. In the *CO₂nv ersando* section, we conducted an interview with Dulce Martínez from Sea Shepherd Mexico, in which we talked about the value of community actions in the care and management of water. In *Yes, yes it is* we have an infographic for you about curious facts about water, another by Laura Escobar about childhood and water, and one more from the Mexican Center for Innovation in Ocean Energy on sargassum. We close with a list of recommendations for texts, videos and conferences to continue exploring the topic of water. We hope you have a pleasant and interesting reading.

From proposal to action: challenges in the implementation of water management projects

Angélica Quevedo Díaz, Gonzalo Río Arronte Foundation, I.A.P.
Jazmín Mota Nieto, University of Edinburgh

Water is an element of nature that can be found in many forms: as a liquid in a river, lake or sea, as a solid in a glacier or a snowflake, or as a gas that condenses in the atmosphere, forming spectacular clouds. Thanks to science, we know that water is also a fundamental factor for life, although its origin and appearance on planet Earth remain mysteries to debate.

Since the first human beings, the hunter-gatherers, water played a primary role in defining the decisions they made because they had to constantly search for how to have access to it. Thus, the existence or lack of water determined where these first groups of people moved, something similar to what other animal and plant species do. The ease of moving from one place to another represented an advantage; however, as they became sedentary and created communities mainly around agricultural activities, great challenges began to arise to ensure access to water in specific and static geographies.

If we take a look at history, many of the great civilizations developed around bodies of water, mainly rivers. Thus, "water cultures" were born that developed different techniques and practices to use water and manage it in such a way that they could meet their needs in agriculture, hygiene and sanitation.

But, there were also - and there are - other places where communities settled, and water resources were scarce; this was not an impediment, but rather, it triggered the creation of other forms of technology and the emergence of rules and mechanisms for its management and administration. For example, in Venice, the drinking water wells and their distribution were in charge of the church, from where their management was decided. In other places in the world and throughout human history, different cultures and civilizations have had to learn how to observe, predict and design mechanisms to ensure water access.

In 2006, the United Nations recognized the relevance of these forms of knowledge by proposing the slogan "*Water and culture*" for World Water Day (March 22). Later, in 2018, within the framework of the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the slogan "*The answer is in nature*" appears, which again launches an invitation to search and recognize the history of the planet and humanity's possible solutions to major problems such as floods, drought and water pollution. It is worth recognizing that the accessibility to or scarcity of water has been a fundamental factor in the evolution and disappearance of civilizations; therefore, we need to implement effective actions around protecting and managing this resource.

How many times have we heard that water is a vital resource, that it is a right and that it is important to care for it? However, water seems more like a luxury than a right. According to data from the United Nations and the SDGs, there are still thousands of people without drinking water and sanitation, mainly in rural areas.

Despite living on a planet where water is abundant, the portion of this resource suitable for human use and consumption is limited and not distributed evenly. In addition to this, many freshwater bodies face great challenges for their extraction and/or strong pollution problems or alterations in their quality, further limiting access to it.

Managing water entails great challenges, from differences in technical, operational, and institutional capabilities, economic resources, and sustainability, among others. Finding solutions to these challenges is not a simple task, as it involves planning and implementation processes for which the appropriate conditions are not always available, or those responsible are not willing to assume their role in a comprehensive and strategic way. What do we mean by this?

We will return to the experience of the Río Arronte Foundation, particularly in the area of water. The foundation is an institution with more than twenty years of work and is a national and international reference on the subject, and has also supported institutions and organizations interested in addressing the challenges associated with water. But behind these actions is a whole effort of planning and teamwork.

The design of a project proposal is not an easy topic since it must be considered that there is a very varied scale of organizations - some very small with a few staff and lack of their own resources, others that are quite the opposite. Many of them require economic resources to survive, and on several occasions, the proposal's design responds more to those needs than to those of the interested parties who require immediate access to water. Therefore, we are facing a complex moment in the life of organizations from different angles.

Additionally, organizations' lack of technical and operational capabilities puts them at high fiscal and legal risk. Due to the workloads, the multiple tasks involved in coordinating and operating projects, and the administrative and accounting issues, organizations encounter problems that put their survival at risk. Likewise, if you want to carry out sustainable and long-term interventions, the process of preparing a proposal can be intensive in time and resources, which also has a series of implications for organizations.

Although the interest in addressing the problems of quality, quantity, management or access to water is a priority, the multiple steps to go from an idea that becomes a proposal and subsequently into action are more complex than we usually imagine.

Experiences indicate that participation is an essential component for the design of proposals, as it allows the involvement of diverse actors, integrates their voices and translates them into actions that, in turn, help to obtain better results. It also allows the development of comprehensive, strategic proposals with great possibilities of success.

Combine the commitment of all those who must contribute both technically and financially to the same purpose, have the authorization and consent of those who will receive the benefit or support, have a very clear diagnosis of the situation or problem that you want to address, as well as establishing a clear theory of change are inputs that we can obtain through active participation. What is sought is to have solid proposals with clear purposes and scope, with measurable, limited commitments, and, above all, not to create false expectations of the projects.

The people in charge of preparing and presenting a proposal have a double responsibility. On the one hand, the institutional purpose must be met; on the other, urgent needs must be fulfilled, leaving aside organizational priorities occasionally. Although it may seem challenging, designing and implementing projects efficiently and with fabulous results is possible.

So we invite all people interested in contributing to reducing the challenges for water management to join in defining clear, transparent and strategic intentions. The potential for collaboration to develop impact projects that integrate knowledge, address the major problems surrounding water resources, and help create positive and sustainable transformations is enormous. There are resources, willingness, and interest; we just need to define the direction we want to point the compass in, and then, let's navigate together.

Angélica Quevedo has been the project coordinator in the water area of the Gonzalo Río Arronte Foundation for 5 years. She has a master's degree in Sustainability Sciences from UNAM with more than 15 years of experience in the environmental sector. She has been in charge of monitoring and coordinating projects in the GRA Foundation, GIZ, UNDP, GEF and the CCA, among other projects.

Do you want to know more about the work of the **Gonzalo Río Arronte Foundation**?

Visit their site:

<https://fundaciongonzalorioarronte.org/>

The Cozumel current: a source of energy for Mexico

Valeria Chávez, Engineering Institute, UNAM, vchavezc@iingen.unam.mx

Ismael Mariño-Tapia, ENES-Mérida, UNAM, imarino@enesmerida.unam.mx

Rodolfo Silva, Engineering Institute, UNAM, rsilvac@iingen.unam.mx

Despite the many and varied potential sources of renewable energy in Mexico, its use is limited by various factors such as the strong dependence of the economy on fossil fuels and the simplicity and low costs of its exploitation given the existing infrastructure; the lack of information and knowledge about renewable energy sources; the limited research capacity and high costs involved in the development of competitive technologies for the production of clean energy; and the social and environmental requirements that new technological developments often impose.

To promote electrical energy generation in an environmentally responsible manner, Mexico established 2008 commitments to reduce energy generation from fossil fuels, giving rise to the decree of the Law for the Use of Renewable Energies and the financing of the Energy Transition. In response, starting in 2013, the Mexican Energy Innovation Centers (CEMIEs) were created. In 2017, CEMIE-Océano began activities led by the UNAM Engineering Institute. CEMIE-Océano has sought to generate innovative products, techniques and technologies to take advantage of the diversity of available ocean energy resources (waves, currents, salinity and temperature gradients, in addition to wind) and thereby contribute in a sustainable, effective and profitable way to satisfy the energy demand in Mexico taking into account the supply chains and the climatic conditions and megadiversity typical of a tropical country.

Given that Mexico has around 2 million people living in communities of less than 100 inhabitants that do not have electricity, CEMIE-Océano has pursued local generation/consumption separate from electrical mega generation. Thus, it was decided to bring together all national technical capabilities and pursue the ultimate goal of providing and deploying technology appropriate to the conditions of the Mexican seas that respects the environment and offers socially responsible solutions despite the limited financing available.

When we talk about the Mexican Caribbean, it is usually related to beaches and tourism, but in addition to that, there is ample potential for energy generation in this region. One of the most relevant projects is using energy from the current of the Cozumel channel. Until now, work has been carried out regarding the physical and ecological characterization of the canal, the energy resource and the development of efficient technology for its use.

Characterization of the Cozumel Channel

The Yucatan Current travels through the Cozumel Channel with average speeds of 0.88 - 1.04 meters per second (m/s). These conditions make this channel a promising site for harnessing the energy of ocean currents, mainly due to its low intermittency.

Shallow water bathymetric¹ data have been collected in various field campaigns, and deep water data from multibeam information from the UNAM oceanographic vessel "Justo Sierra" in 2019. The resource assessment of ocean currents in the Mexican Caribbean, emphasising the Island of Cozumel, will conclude in 2022. This evaluation was carried out at different spatial scales, evaluating ocean currents in deep waters using a validated and adjusted medium-scale numerical method, and for smaller depths (at 20m), the combined effects of waves and turbulence with nested numerical models that include scale resolutions of turbines and their effects. Carrying out an analysis at different depths is essential to understand the impacts of the projects.

Energy generation from ocean currents has great benefits as it is clean energy and considerably reduces greenhouse gas emissions. However, it also raises concerns about its environmental impacts, including the likelihood of collision of marine mammals and large fish, noise propagation, alteration of larval dispersal patterns, alteration of coastal morphology and sedimentation patterns, and the effects on oceanographic processes.

Since almost 80% of Cozumel is designated as a protected natural area, the potential site for the placement of technology to harness the current is the area between two reserves (the Natural Protected Area of Flora and Fauna of the Island of Cozumel and the Parque Cozumel Reef National Park). Species such as dolphins, sea turtles, sharks and whale sharks are known to reside near and around the island, but more so on the eastern side.

Development of a turbine for the Cozumel Channel

Given the characteristics of the current speed of the Cozumel channel, which is considered low compared to the design speeds of existing current turbines, CEMIE-Océano focused on developing an adequate and efficient turbine for these conditions. A small-scale model (16 cm diameter by 16 cm high) was built and tested using the channel of the Coastal and Port Laboratory of the UNAM Engineering Institute. Subsequently, a 1 m diameter vertical axis helical# turbine prototype was designed and built at the UNAM Engineering Institute. In 2021, experimental testing of this prototype was carried out at the Kelvin Hydrodynamic Laboratory at the University of Strathclyde, United Kingdom.

In 2022, field tests were carried out by the Engineering Institute, UNAM, to evaluate performance in different conditions in Lake Tequesquitengo, Morelos, Mexico. To carry out these tests, it was necessary to design and build a catamaran² in order to hold the turbine while it was towed. The towing operation was executed in stable water conditions at constant speeds, resulting in relative speeds between 0.6 and 1.2 m/s. Likewise, in 2022, an evaluation of the performance of a wind-driven turbine under variable speed conditions was carried out.

¹ Referring to "bathymetry" which is the measurement of ocean depth.

² A catamaran is a vessel that, unlike traditional single-hull boats, has two parallel hulls that are connected by a deck or platform. This design has the advantage of greater stability, speed and amplitude than traditional boats.

The impacts of the projects and their evaluation

Regarding environmental impacts, in 2021, a study was carried out to determine the effects on the currents of the Cozumel channel due to the presence of a large number of turbines (~5,300 turbines) for the “collection” of energy. On the other hand, experiments are being developed (on-site and in the laboratory) to evaluate changes in the behavior of fish with and without this vertical axis turbine operating at different speeds. These tests will be carried out as soon as the permits required for the placement and testing of the turbine prototype at sea are approved by the Mexican authorities.

Another important aspect has been to evaluate and work on the Cozumel community's perception regarding installing a turbine in the canal. To achieve this, surveys and meetings have been carried out with the local community. One of the activities carried out was the exhibition “The Cozumel Current: a source of Clean Energy”, which took place in the Quintana Roo Park in 2022. In this event, researchers from the CEMIE-Océano project showed children, young people and adults a prototype of the turbine and explained its operation, as well as the different technical, environmental and social aspects that are being considered in its development.

If you want to know more about this and other CEMIE-Océano projects, we invite you to visit their page and consult the newsletters and materials that are published:

<https://cemieoceano.mx/>

References

- Energy Yield Assessment from Ocean Currents in the Insular Shelf of Cozumel Island.
- Impacto de grandes campos de hidrogeneradores en el Canal de Cozumel a través de modelación numérica.
- Potential sites for the use of ocean energy in the Mexican Caribbean.
- Experiments to characterise a vertical axis helical turbine (pp- 11-12).
- Performance evaluation of 1 meter-diameter vertical axis helical turbine (pp. 85-86).
- Exposición “La corriente de Cozumel: una fuente de energía limpia”. Boletín CEMIE-Océano, Año 5 No. 1, pp. 38-39.
- IEA-OES (2022): Annual Report: An Overview of Ocean Energy Activities in 2021.

CONVERSING

Every drop is valuable, and so is every voice

Interview with **Dulce Martínez, Sea Shepherd México**
By **Lorena Morales**

Undoubtedly, one of the essential resources for life and for all the activities we carry out is water. Pollution of water bodies is a severe problem in which people and communities play a significant role. On this occasion, we spoke with Dulce Martínez from Sea Shepherd, Mexico, who has extensive experience and knowledge and works with non-governmental organizations and communities.

Dulce Martínez is a passionate environmental advocate focused on social work and permaculture, culture and arts projects. She is a biologist by training and is in the process of obtaining her Master's Degree in Sustainable Societies. She has a DiveMaster certification and experience in underwater activities. She has stood out in projects for organizations such as "Casa de las Lunas" Semillas de Agua, Damos de Corazón, Oaxaca con Fruto Raíz, Eco constructores Oaxaca, Meshico tu causa es mi causa, among others. Additionally, she collaborated as National Deputy Coordinator at Sea Shepherd Mexico for three years. Her experience ranges from producing documentaries to organizing charity events and speaking at conservation conferences. She has project consulting and organizational management skills, highlighting her dedication to conservation.

We hope you enjoy this interview.

L: Dulce, could you tell us about your career, personal and professional, and how your interest in water issues and the focus on communities arose?

D: I am a biologist from the UAM Iztapalapa. I delved into environmental issues, especially in urban contexts, by participating in several campaigns, one for Seashepard México. Another topic I have worked on is the conservation of bodies of water, which involves a lot of problems, both in rural and urban environments. Many official Mexican concessions and regulations regarding water pollution are not followed. In Mexico, there is legislation, but there is no one to supervise, monitor and implement it properly. I have been working on this topic for more than 10 years; it is a long road where the social aspect is very relevant since I have worked a lot for civil society organizations doing research, reading books, analyzing complaints and reports and learning about the problems of rivers and basins, particularly in Mexico City.

L: At what point does the role of the community enter your work and career?

D: When in my work I read and compile information study official Mexican regulations and public policies around the issue of water, I realize that all of this is related to and directly affects the people who live near rivers and bodies of water and that the opinions of these communities are critical. So, inevitably, we began to have a closer relationship with the people and decision-makers in some projects.

Working with government agencies, civil society, communities and populations has gradually increased. For me, working with communities is very fascinating. Some people have incredible projects and ideas in their localities and are passionate about defending their territory and its resources. They have a very deep-rooted identity, and I find that beautiful. Many do not base their lives on the traditional economic model but on their roots and the primary and secondary identity relationships of their places of origin.

L: What are the main challenges you have faced working with civil society to address water problems?

D: Working with multiple instances is always complex. Each one brings their agenda to fulfil, which makes it challenging to achieve the goals that each person visualizes; therefore, agile methodologies are needed to align them. Within the same groups, there are political agendas from different periods. For example, a municipality has an annual plan may include cleaning the river with monthly campaigns to collect a ton of urban solid waste, putting into service a well that was not working, or other actions.

But right in that same municipality, a group of community members or ejidatarios has plans, perhaps for 3 or 5 years, with other initiatives or interventions. One is the keline model, which allows you to adapt the land so that water passes through particular places and can remain a little longer on Earth to favor humidity conditions, microbiomes, reforestation, etc.

Differences in objectives and time may conflict, and it is necessary to initiate the corresponding negotiations so that the parties involved can reach an agreement.

L: How can we help improve awareness about the issue of water, which may be linked to other social and/or environmental problems?

D: Water is the basis of almost all our cyclical and biological processes on Earth. With this in mind, a water pollution or management problem will have a knock-on effect. For example, the Lerma River is one of the most polluted in Mexico. The Lerma-Chapala basin is the one that provides water to Mexico City and metropolitan areas; by the time it passes through Toluca, it is already polluted because the river meets many industries in the State of Mexico and Michoacán which discharge waste from the agroindustry and textiles in it. There are also illegal livestock discharges.

The more contaminated the bodies of water are, the more the problems with flora and fauna and the effects on the ecosystems that depend on said resource worsen. Waste dumped into rivers, lakes and seas also generates large quantities of greenhouse gases, exacerbating climate change. If discharges are not controlled, many contaminants will remain in the water, permeating and damaging the soil and all the biota that depend on it. Trees get sick, and their oxygen production and carbon capture decrease because everything is interconnected.

Water pollution and quality problems are utterly essential to address and should be a priority since they directly impact human health and ecosystems. The effects of pollution always come back to us in many ways: in our food, what we breathe or where we live. If we do not address these situations, sooner or later, they will generate a more severe problem.

L: How can pollution caused by industry be regulated? How could we make information about the impact of water pollution known?

D: The industry is already aware of the consequences of water pollution; it is not that they have not realized it, it is not that they do not know, and it is not that the standards or legislation do not exist. All this is known, and little is done since we are subject to the global economic systems we subscribe to. Capitalism is the central system in the world; no one is outside it.

What we need is awareness. Little by little, we understand better the consequences of contaminating water, and with this, we can generate strategies, information, and infrastructure to solve the problem. It is necessary to move to different solutions and economic models. Therefore, I encourage us to join this paradigm shift and understand that change always occurs, and we must be ready to face it and adapt.

SÍ, SÍ ES

YES, YES IT IS

FACTS YOU SHOULD KNOW ABOUT WATER

The Earth should be called the **WATER** planet

75% of the planet's surface is covered by water, of which **96.5%** are seas and oceans

3.5% is freshwater, but only **0.25%** is drinking water

Access to water is a luxury.
3 out of every 10 people in the world do not have access to drinking water in their homes.

By 2025, **2/3** of the world's population may face problems due to water stress.

The pollution problem.
80% of the planet's wastewater is discharged into the environment contaminated.

Excessive consumption.
Water, like other resources, is consumed excessively while others do not even have access to it.

According to the Observatory of Socio-Environmental Conflicts of Mexico, there are **333** water-related conflicts in the territory.

Diet counts.
It is estimated that **70%** of the planet's freshwater is used for agricultural and livestock activities.

References:
<https://www.nationalgeographic.es/photoaquae/2019/03/11-datos-interes-santes-sobre-el-agua>
<https://images.vexels.com/media/users/3/139498/raw/c2da0bc8e20334e3f7497d454efab2c8-world-water-day-infographic.jpg>
<https://agua.org.mx/editoriales/conflictos-por-el-agua-en-mexico-causas-y-reacciones/>

SÍ, SÍ ES

YES, YES IT IS

WATER AND CHILDREN

By **Laura Escobar Colmenares**

All people have the right to quality water, which can be consumed and allows us to address our daily life needs and tasks¹.

Access to water is also a children's right!

However, girls and boys are at greater risk of contracting diseases that are transmitted through of the water.

95 thousand kids under five years of age die every year from **consuming contaminated water** in Mexico².

66 % of the national territory is affected by some degree of water scarcity³.

How to guarantee the right to water?

The responsibility lies with the State, but also with society and we have to act collectively and promote participation in the care of water from the local level.

What can we do together with children?

- **Inform** us about the water situation where we live.
- **Involve** children in caring for water in homes, schools and the community.
- **Modify** consumption habits.
- **Promote** a community environmental ethic.
- **Use eco-techniques** for the most efficient water use: dry toilets and water harvesting.
- **Demand** from governments for a fair and equitable distribution of water.
- **Resist** the dispossession practices of extractive companies and projects that steal and contaminate bodies of water.

References

- ¹ Pedrozo Acuña, A. (2020). El consumo global del agua y la sustentabilidad. *Perspectivas IMTA*, 1(14). <https://doi.org/10.24850/b-imta-perspectivas-2020-14>
- ² Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México. Dirección de Comunicación Social. (2019). LANZA UNAM CAMPAÑA DE AHORRO DEL AGUA [Página Web UNAM]. Boletín UNAM-DGCS. https://www.dgcs.unam.mx/boletin/bdboletin/2019_196.html
- ³ Rojas, A. (2023, junio 22). Alcanza escasez de agua al 65.59% del territorio mexicano [Portal de noticias]. *El Economista*. <https://www.eleconomista.com.mx/politica/Alcanza-escasez-de-agua-al-65.59-del-territorio-mexicano-20230622-0001.html>

SÍ, SÍ ES

YES, YES IT IS

SARGASSUM IN THE MEXICAN CARIBBEAN

Sargassum fluitans y *S. natans* (sargassum) are species of floating brown algae found in the Atlantic, concentrated in the Sargasso Sea and, since 2011, in the Great Atlantic Sargassum Belt.

One of the main challenges in understanding the dynamics of sargassum and facing the challenges of its management is the difficulty in predicting when and how much sargassum will reach the coasts.

To date, Mexico does not have an official national strategy for sargassum management including its collection, storage, valorization and disposal.

However, Mexico has the technical, scientific, industrial and market capacity to generate effective and lasting solutions that can be adapted in many countries that face the same challenge.

Negative impacts:

- Flora and fauna death
- Beach erosion and pollution
- Decline in tourism
- High management costs

Field observations, analysis of satellite images and numerical models are useful to understand the dynamics of sargassum.

References

Wang, M., et al. (2019). The great Atlantic Sargassum belt. *Science* 365(6448), 83-87.

Chávez, V., et al. (2020). Massive Influx of Pelagic Sargassum spp. on the Coasts of the Mexican Caribbean 2014–2020: Challenges and Opportunities, *Water*, 12(10).

Uribe-Martínez, A., et al. (2022) Multiscale distribution patterns of pelagic rafts of sargasso (*Sargassum* spp.) in the Mexican Caribbean (2014-2020). *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 1609.

López-Miranda, JL, et al. (2021) Commercial Potential of Pelagic Sargassum spp. in Mexico, *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 8:768470.

PARA LLEVAR TAKE-AWAY

In this section, we leave you a list of suggestions and recommendations to continue learning and reflecting on the topic of water and information about a couple of conferences that may interest you.

Book: *Geological Adventures: Water*

This book is produced and published by the Colombian Association of Petroleum Geologists and Geophysicists (ACGP), authored by Linda Cárdenas and illustrated by Lorena Manrique; it is a dissemination and pedagogy project that talks about and shows basic and relevant information about water accompanied by colorful and attractive images that will take you on a geological adventure to learn more about water, its origin, use and how to care for it. You can download the book at the following link:

<https://acggp.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/08/acggp-aventuras-geologicas-agua-libro1.pdf>

Magazine of the University: *Water*

We invite you to download and read the No.861 issue of the Magazine of the University (La Revista de la Universidad) dedicated to water, in which you will find information, poems and notes that will provide you with interesting data and reflections on such resource.

<https://www.revistadelauniversidad.mx/releases/52ef915f-1f21-4274-a3c2-3fe91a1d29bb/agua>

Movie: *Mad Max - Fury Road*

This movie presents a world different from the one we know, in which there is a crisis and constant struggle for water, in addition to other social conflicts that the societies in this film portray. Humanity has stopped fighting for the "so precious" oil; water is now the greatest need.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hEJnMQG9ev8>

Documentary: *Who owns the water?*

This documentary presents how water is a fundamental resource for practically all the activities we carry out and how the purchase of water rights by large industries occurs, leaving farmers and citizens with no access to water. You can find this and other documentaries about water on the DW Documental YouTube channel.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jIZYsRDw2QM>

PARA LLEVAR TAKE-AWAY

Interactive portal: *AGUA.org.mx*

This portal is a project of the Fund for Communication and Environmental Education, A.C. and was created in 2004 thanks to the sponsorship of the Gonzalo Río Arronte Foundation. It is dedicated to publishing documents and materials related to water and its management. It has a collection of more than 40,000 books and materials, and more than 500,000 information points about the national territory. If you are looking for information about water in Mexico, we recommend you visit this portal:

<https://agua.org.mx>

Publication: *Community Water Management*

This publication presents a series of articles that discuss and make visible how community water systems fulfil a critical task in managing water resources in Mexico. Do you want to learn more about this approach and the experiences of various projects and communities in Mexico? Download the publication at the following link:

<https://agua.org.mx/biblioteca/gestion-comunitaria-del-agua-articulo/>

CCUS Latin American Conference, Brazil 2024

We invite you to the CCUS Latin American Congress that will take place on May 22 and 23, 2024, in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil. For more information on submitting jobs and registration, see the following:

<https://ccusevent.org/latinamerica/2024>

Latin American CCS Network

With the purpose of uniting efforts, experience and knowledge, the Mexican CCS Platform, MeCCS, leads the initiative to create the Latin American CCS Network. If you want to be part of it, we invite you to send your expression of interest at the following link:

<https://forms.gle/kMMKE1ApxdwfvqfWA>

Mexico City, Mexico, 2024